

Professional Development and Challenges Faced by Academic Women Librarians in 21 century (2010- 2022): A Literature Review

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Abstract:-

Objective: This writing literature review gives a framework for understanding the professional development of academic women librarians in academic libraries and the challenges they face in the workplace. This study divided the literature review into national and international levels from 2010 to 2022.

Methods: Sources are selected from primary bibliographies on women's status, progress, Professional development, and academic libraries. Print and online resources, research manuscripts of journals, periodical articles, books, e-books, and dissertations are referred for research related to these topics from 2010 to 2022. The review of related literature is categorized at the National and International levels.

Results: Evidence suggests that a number of personal and professional characteristics of women librarians could be recognized. Evidence from the 2010s to the present shows an increase in the number of women in librarianship. As a woman in librarianship in professional development and career progression, she faced challenges such as health issues, housing responsibilities, mobility, career breaks, and a lack of organizational support. Women have expanded their knowledge of ITC activities at the same time. Today's female librarians are technologically competent. The growth of digital technology facilitates women's successful participation in the field of library science's professional development.

These reviews of related literature were included to underline the importance of the subject of professional development of women librarians and the challenges faced by them.

Conclusion: Different surveys of female librarians and professional development have been observed in more developed countries. Women still make up more than 80% of librarianship. However, it is felt that this profession is suitable for women at the national and international levels because of its feminine value. Most studies have stressed that the organization and the library professionals are jointly responsible for striving toward professional development.

Keywords:- Professional development, women Librarians, Academic Institutions, National Level, International level, E-books.

I. INTRODUCTION

The literature review provides some insight into the strong points and limitations of the previous studies. It enables them to improve their investigation and arrive at the proper perspective of the study. Thus this review of literature covers studies made from 2010 to 2022 at the national and international levels.

This review of literature studies and observations on the professional development areas related to women's librarians and the attitude of women librarians toward participation in professional development activities, and challenges faced by them.

The topic "Professional Development and challenges faced by women Librarians" has been studied universally. Very few research studies have been conducted between 2010 to 2022, at the National level compared to the international level. A review of related literature consisted of print and online resources, i.e., research manuscripts of journals, periodical articles, books, e-books, dissertations, and Thesis. A survey of the literature available in India (National) and abroad (International) is presented under the subheading listed below.

- Women Librarian
- Professional Development of Women Librarians
- Challenges Faced by Women Librarians.

II. WOMEN LIBRARIANS

A. The National Level review of related literature on women librarians

In 2015, Mathew, Sheeja & Nellickal studied the women LIS professionals of 7 major universities in Kerala to assess their ICT skills with the help of structured questionnaires. The study reveals that male professionals have slightly better skills in I.C.T.-based applications than females. The male professionals had good skills in I.C.T.-based services than female Librarians. 28% had a low level of awareness, and the rest, 18.7% and 16%, did not use or are unaware of the same. Female professionals had good skills, and the rest had low awareness or skills in I.C.T.-based services.

Vijayakumar & Anthony (2015) mentioned that women library professionals determine their ICT literacy skills. The study reveals that Women LIS professionals have average skills in computer networking, bar code scanners, image scanners, Linux, MS Office, and above-average skills in the Internet and windows. Most female professionals know about digital library software D-Space,

KOHA, and library networks. Few professionals have I.C.T.-based information retrieval skills (accessing, searching, and using E-journals), electronic document delivery, and interlibrary loan through the web and online Indexing and abstracting services.

A different study by Lijina & Jalaja (2015), was done on the usage of mass media among women LIS professionals from the University of Calicut and Kerala university. The study reveals that most women LIS professionals use social networking sites and search engines. Nearly half of them use internet services like newsgroups, downloading software/ programs, online shopping, and chatting. They also use YouTube, Internet Banking, online ticket booking, and Blogging. The respondents' favorite areas of information and the problems they face in the usage of mass media are examined in the study.

The study is based on mentioned that Indian women serving as library and information science professionals are content and comfortable working in the current library environment. Kumbhar (2016) stated that most of them are with whatever facilities and remuneration are extended to them. Usually, they do not see beyond the societal norms, given the liberal and understanding social fabric of Indian society. But LIS Academic training in professional and personal competencies will equip women librarians to compete for higher positions in all types of libraries.

In her article, Tank (2016) said, "Most women in all professions, not just in librarianship, find it difficult to balance career and family, which hinders their personal career growth or leads to broken relationships, leading to stress and health issues. Women need to understand the harmony in ourselves as an Individual, harmony in the family, in society, and with Nature/existence to live our lives according to our Natural Acceptance,". She wrote this statement about women and librarianship, an opportunity to transcend and understand harmony, roles, responsibility, and values discussed in most literature on women and librarianship.

Parikh (2016) gives many examples of the Women librarians' contribution from abroad and in India: scenario. She stated that "there will be more contribution from females librarians towards Knowledge Centers if women in India are given the necessary support to develop the capacity to contribute to India's knowledge. But at the same time, female and male librarians are important to contribute to librarianship. A library that caters to men and women can provide better service with staff whose key positions will be divided between the sex. Men and women represent different elements; they see things from different perspectives. If they work together in a separate library, each contributes their best; The result is broader, richer, and more diverse than if only men or women were involved. "A different survey was conducted by Sawant (2018) on women librarians' opinions about apparel for daily use and their preferences for special occasions such as conferences/ workshops/meetings, etc. The study explored tattooing styles and jewelry used by women library professionals. Jewelry and other accessories were preferred by a moderate

number of respondents, whereas tattooing practice was absent. An average number of women librarians selected jewelry and other accessories, whereas, in tattooing practice, women librarians are not more interested. In the case of stereotyping of librarians, respondents felt that librarians have not been stereotyped in media as far as Indian media is concerned.

B. The International Level review of related literature on women librarians

Bergman (2010) aims to review the history of gender inequity in libraries, outline salary issues in libraries, and attempt to define systems librarians use for comparison. This study surveyed for gender, salary, and other demographic information to determine whether gender equity or gender stratification is occurring within their specialty. Most women librarians work in the USA, but 20 percent work worldwide. Results indicate that males are not favored over females for employment in this library specialty. Experience and geographic location were the only significant factors affecting salary. The distinction between public and technical services appears to be blurred by electronic resource management. To determine whether the computerization of library resources is altering the concept of what librarians do and what libraries are, it could be useful to look more closely at this blurring.

The study analyzed by Moran, Leonard, and Zellers (2010) on parity between men and women administration in academic libraries. They found that equality between women and men administrators had not been accomplished. Women holding directorships increased from the year 1972 to the year 2009, attributing the change to the high turnover of director positions between 1994 and 2009 and the number of women who replaced men as they vacated the director role. They noted that the trend can still be improved if women are as proportionally represented in academic administrator positions as in the profession.

The study examined the "feminization" of Librarianship by Mars (2018), which continues to influence the gender pay gap and the extreme leadership bias in the area today. It also examines the stereotyping of librarians and the cyclical effect of gendering the profession. Additionally, this article explores options for combating the gender perceptions that negatively impact women in library and information science fields, including management and negotiation training in graduate programs, increased emphasis on technological skills, and professional organization advocacy.

This study highlights areas and research topics that have significantly broadened gender expertise and impact at the highest administrative levels. Bladdek (2019) focuses on an overview of gender and leadership theories before retracing the research on gender-specific career models described in the work of Schiller (1974) and other gender-related issues, the lack of diversity among female university librarians and library management, including leadership styles, perceptions of differences between men and women. The librarianship in the 21st is active, vibrant, a living foundation of good influences, and a service-oriented

institution with goals to achieve trans-formative technological know-how. Olanrewaju (2020) said that the new outlook exited through formal education extended to the females provides the gateway for talented women to prove themselves. This study investigates women's roles and impacts in selected tertiary institutions in Ogun State. He shows that more female Librarians occupy leadership ladders now than before.

III. PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN LIBRARIANS

A. *The National Level review of related literature on Professional Development of Women Librarians*

Tiwari and Borse(2015) studied the occupational growth of women librarians working in affiliated colleges under the directorate of higher education in Mumbai and Konkan. The study focused on women's academic and professional qualifications in librarianship. It found that women are satisfied in their present profession. They found that most women librarians have joined this profession only because of their interests. Most women librarians actively participate in various professional activities, but their publishing ratio is very low, which must be increased. The majority of women librarians are satisfied with their current job. Studying the occupational status of women librarians due to gender discrimination in Indian society is quite interesting and useful.

This study is showcased by Gul et al. (2016), on the influence of gender in library management and information science. From the author's point of view, the study researched and reviewed articles published between 2005 and 2014 in electronic libraries, lending libraries, and an information science journal. The study looked at the status of women in research, particularly in the areas of library and information science. Its results are based on the contributions of the relevant authors in the journal "Electronic Libraries." Readers are encouraged to expand their research to include contributing authors to other information science libraries and journals. This study highlights the involvement and influence of female authors in library research and information science.

Future libraries are new information hubs that rely heavily on information technology for practically all of their operations. Future library services require different talents than those needed today. Future female librarians must be as adept in this new information technology environment to achieve the prominence they merit. The development of digital technology enables women to actively participate in science and technology decision-making and implementation, including planning and prioritizing research and development, as well as choosing, acquiring, adapting, innovating, and applying science and technology for development (Devraju, 2017).

B. *International level literature review on the professional development of Women Librarians*

The article was written by Downey (2011), on the history, development, and issues of female librarians in librarianship. He understands well that their high level of education, intelligence, leadership, seniority, thoughtfulness, and many other qualities are required to perform their jobs satisfactorily. However, most of the public is still not aware of their skills. He said Librarians are still underpaid for the work they do. Scholars and researchers believe that these injustices lie because it is a woman-owned profession.

With the help of interviews, Nakhoda and Rahiman (2015) studied the women librarians' promoting and inhibiting factors on their professional development; this study focuses on the influential control factors that help empower female librarians. Interviews revealed that job skills, participation and teamwork, role resolution, access to information, motivation, role modeling, recognition, and appreciation were influential factors in female librarians' empowerment. From the point of view of female public library managers, poor organizational system, negative attitude towards staff, and pedagogical management style are among the factors inhibiting the assignment of women librarians.

Research has been done by Khan and Du (2017), on the several factors affecting the use of social networks for professional development among women librarians in Pakistan. These factors include social characteristics such as private life, parental education, marital status, and family support. The aim was to explore how Pakistani librarians use social media for professional development and their perception of its usefulness. This study examines social characteristics, social networks, and their relationship with PD. The majority of Pakistani librarians regularly use social networks. However, social networks are considered less useful for learning technical skills.

The investigation of the current status and occupational characteristics of professional librarians in Ghana was done by Adjah and Walt (2019). He also seeks to establish their career advancement opportunities and explores the factors that hinder their career growth. The study sought information on the background of female librarians in Ghana, their professional experience, status, and opportunities for career advancement. The study was to find out how their male colleagues perceived them. The results showed that they did not experience any form of discrimination from their male colleagues.

Ashiqet al. (2021) explore women's leadership role in academic libraries in Pakistan. It examines the key challenges female leaders face in their rise to the top, a key indicator of success, their work, and the community service and professional contributions they made during their careers. The results indicate that organizational challenges, family responsibilities, and gender discrimination hinder female leaders' professional development. Critical indicators of their success are an effective use of technology, professional commitment, academic contribution, community service, family support, international exposure,

and lifelong learning; the implications of the study highlight different areas of improvement for female librarians.

In another study of women's skills required by women's leaders by Yang & Wang (2013), university libraries focused on female leaders in the university library. He investigated the skills needed by women's leaders in Swedish university libraries. The results of their research and conclusions are attractive. They concluded that experts in male and female libraries should have similar skills. They do not find any skills that are required exclusively by library experts. But they observed that women have an advantage in interpersonal effectiveness. Again, this leads to the fact that female librarians can make a good contribution because of the individual skills they have.

IV. CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN LIBRARIANS

A. *The National Level review of related literature on challenges faced by women Librarians*

Women librarians have the right to participate in professional development, but achieving women's librarian equal participation remains an ongoing challenge, especially in decision-making. The status of women in librarianship can't be assessed without considering women's general position in society and the relative positioning of librarianship. The actual quality of the women in any organization will mean the power enjoyed, followed by the prestige and privileges. Increased awareness of gender bias is needed by all persons concerned in the selection of top-level posts. An organization should organize suitable training facilities relevant to women's special needs at the local level so they can handle the new environment in Libraries (Pattan, 2016).

Examine the factors influencing the career advancement activities of women library professionals by Dhanshree and Devi (2019); They analyzed Factors such as the professional and personal, the influence of professional associations, the impact of ICT & social media, and barriers faced in career progression. The study revealed that professional factors & ICT positively influenced the women library professionals' career advancement activities. Gender discrimination is the main obstacle faced in career progression activities.

B. *The International Level review of related literature on challenges faced by women Librarians*

The current status and professional characteristics of university librarians in Nigeria were studied by Nwezeh (2010). It discusses the concept of gender participation in library science and its effects on the profession as it relates to women. He found that the status of female librarians was not threatened in terms of remuneration and position. It should be noted that despite various obstacles, and barriers that prevent women from participating effectively, they are still making progress professionally. Whether female librarians advance in their careers or not is entirely the decision of professional women themselves. He also found little difference between men's and women's attitudes towards their careers regarding ambition, aspiration, or commitment.

Research on a literature review on the professional development of women librarians by DeLong (2012), shows that the number of women in leadership positions has steadily increased. From the 1930s to the 1950s, it was evident that men headed academic libraries and extensive research libraries. These studies from the 1960s to the 1980s provide evidence that women librarians can identify different personal and occupational characteristics. Women still occupy a low percentage of leadership positions in academic libraries. Although women have increased the number of leadership positions in academic libraries in the United States and Canada, they are still underrepresented. The results section concludes with a review of relevant sources for writing about female librarians. This shows that the professional life of female librarians is greatly misunderstood, as well as the importance of their contribution to library development and librarianship management.

Investigated the current status and job-related challenges of professional academic women librarians at Pakistan's top-ranked the University of Punjab, Lahore, by Yousaf et al. (2013). This research also looks at the general female librarian's experience and alternative solutions that might aid in their professional development. The investigation was carried out utilizing a quantitative approach. According to the responses, the study found that Working women in Pakistan are not subjected to harassment or threats from male co-workers. Yet, cultural features still influence a woman's management position in Pakistan.

Rutledge(2020) explored the study of women academic librarians and their career progressions. By learning more about the barriers that female academic librarians face in managerial positions and the success factors that make female academic librarians successful. This study helped women academic librarians understand obstacles that may discourage their advancement to management positions. It also helped managers, human resources personnel, and deans develop interventions to encourage women's persistence in management positions. Such research is an opportunity to explore how our expertise can limit the negative outcomes of gender behavioral expectations and create an environment for "leaders, male or female, or those who do not recognize themselves in this way, are greatly appreciated." bring to their organization."

A Survey on the work-life balance among married female academic librarians at university libraries in South-East Nigeria (Ibegbulam and Ejikeme,2021). This survey examined how respondents feel about work-life balance regarding family and organizational concerns. The findings show that married female academic librarians have a good attitude toward the family and administrative aspects of work-life balance; however, the organizational factor has a higher mean score than the family factor. The study identifies solutions that could improve respondents' work-life balance and suggests practices and policies. However, this study suggests that married academic librarians value work-life balance in their personal and professional lives; there is little doubt that there is still space for improvement.

V. REMARKABLE FACTORS OF THE PRESENTED STUDY

Based on these findings from the above reviews, the following conclusion can be made;

- There are many studies carried out on women and librarianship and the professional development of women librarians.
- The above literature review described studies on the professional development of women librarians and the challenges they faced; Across the world, including Nigeria, Korea, Ghana, Pakistan, and India. More research has been done on the professional development of women librarians and challenges at the international level compared to the national level.
- Studies published internationally examined male and female librarians' personal and professional characteristics. Comparably India, there is more study done on a global level. Their social-economic status effect women's librarianship.
- At the international level, more women library professionals are satisfied with their working situation, but in India, most women librarians are unsatisfied with their present working conditions.
- Several factors include social characteristics such as private life, parental education, marital status, and family support are affected on professional development.
- There is a difference between attitudes of men and women's towards their careers regarding ambition, aspiration, or commitment at the National and International levels.
- Married female academic librarians have a good attitude toward the family and administrative aspects of work-life balance;
- The professional life of female librarians is greatly misunderstood, as well as the importance of their contribution to library development and librarianship management.
- In light of the findings mentioned above, it is observed that many factors reduce the professional development of women librarians.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study cited in the literature review indicates that considerable work has been done in studying the professional development of women librarians and the challenges women librarians face in their work across the world. Different surveys of female librarians and professional development have been observed in more developed countries. Women still make up more than 80% of librarianship. However, it is felt that this profession is suitable for women at the national and international levels because of its feminine value. Various studies have researched librarians' professional development activities and continuing education needs of women librarians. organizational challenges, family responsibilities, and gender discrimination hinder female leaders' professional development Most studies have stressed that the organization and the library professionals are jointly responsible for striving toward professional development.

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